

Ageing@Work

Smart, Personalized and Adaptive ICT Solutions for Active, Healthy and Productive Ageing with enhanced Workability

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Deliverable D8.4

Ageing@Work Communication and Dissemination Activities report V1

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Executive Summary

This document presents the results of the dissemination and communication activities that have been carried out until June 2020 (project M18) within the framework of the Ageing@Work project. These activities correspond to Task 8.1 "Awareness raising and dissemination strategy" and Task 8.2 "Ageing@Work events, knowledge transfer and networking", of Work Package (WP) 8 "Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Business Planning".

This document presents the different activities carried out in the field of communication and dissemination of the project, including the visual identity, the activities carried through the different dissemination channels, such as web portal, social networks, newsletters, and publications, synergies with other projects and the dissemination through the channels of the European Union. It also presents the progression of the dissemination activities according to the performance indicators set for this activity.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable, entitled “D8.4 Ageing@Work Communication and Dissemination Activities report” aims to present the communication and dissemination activities that have been carried out so far (M18) in the framework of the Ageing@Work project. It should not be forgotten that these activities have been developed following a common Dissemination, Awareness raising and Communication Plan (DACP) developed and presented in D8.1, with the following dissemination objectives:

- To effectively promote the project and its outcomes to all possible target groups / audiences in a national and a European level;
- To establish links and liaisons with international organizations and other interested stakeholders in order to provide wider dissemination;
- To establish synergies with other relevant projects and initiatives;
- To validate the project outcomes, in order to obtain feedback from expert groups, scientists and interested user communities.

1.2 Relation to other activities and deliverables

This report will serve to present the impact on communication and dissemination that the project is having in different areas. This deliverable includes the communication and dissemination activities foreseen in Task 8.1 “Awareness raising and dissemination strategy” and the workshops and participation in events foreseen in Task 8.2 “Ageing@Work events, knowledge transfer and networking”. It is also based on the DACP presented in D8.1 on M3 and updated on M18. It also presents the progress that has been made on the project's web portal, initially presented at D8.2 at M5. It should be said that an update of this report, or rather a second version, will take place in D8.8 in M36 (at the end of the project), compiling all the activities carried out in the field of communication and dissemination.

1.3 Structure of the deliverable

Taking into account the previously described, this report is structured as follows:

Chapter 1. Introduction: Provides information about the scope of the report, its structure and its relationship with other activities and deliverables.

Chapter 2. Dissemination activities: Presents the different activities carried out in the field of communication and dissemination of the project, including the visual identity, the activities carried through the different dissemination channels, synergies with other projects and the dissemination through the channels of the European Union.

Chapter 3. Performance indicators and monitoring: Presents the progression of the dissemination activities according to the performance indicators (KPIs) set for the communication and dissemination activities.

Chapter 4. Conclusions: Presents the conclusions of the activities carried out and analyses in which areas it is necessary to make a greater effort in the communication and dissemination of the project.

2. Dissemination activities

2.1 Visual identity and promotional package

Since the beginning of the project, different work has been done on the visual identity of Ageing@Work, which is key for an effective dissemination of the project so the different materials developed in the framework of the project can be easily identified and related to the project itself. In addition, different elements have been developed for the promotion and dissemination of Ageing@Work, including the logo, leaflet and poster, which are described in the following sub-sections.

2.1.1 Logo

Firstly, the project logo was developed, which can be seen in figure 1, with the agreement of all partners. The colors chosen in the logo have been used as a visual reference in the different materials developed to promote the project.

Figure 1. Ageing@Work's logo

2.1.2 Leaflet

A project leaflet has been prepared using the logo's visual identity colours. The leaflet describes the aim and goals of Ageing@Work, the partners that make up the project Consortium, the ICT tools that are being developed in the project with the expected beneficiaries and benefits that these tools will provide, the project identity data with the reference to the European Union's funding, the contact details and the website and social networks, through which anyone can follow the project outcomes. The following figures show an image of both sides of the leaflet, which has been provided to all partners for dissemination.

OUR AIM

Is to help ageing workers of the modern industry to maintain productivity and workability for longer, while achieving a balance between work and personal life, through the fusion of smart working and living environments and highly adaptive personalized ICT tools.

PROJECT PARTNERS

	CENTER FOR RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY HELLAS www.certh.gr Greece
	UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID www.upm.es Spain
	SIEMENS AG www.siemens.com/global/en Germany
	MYSPHERA SL mysphera.com Spain
	UNIVERSITY OF PATRAS www.upatras.gr/en Greece
	SAMSUNG ELECTRONICS (UK) LTD www.samsung.com/uk United Kingdom
	CENTRALNY INSTYTUT OCHRONY PRACY – PAŃSTWOWY INSTYTUT BADAWCZY www.ciop.pl/en Poland
	INSTITUTE FOR OCCUPATIONAL MEDICINE, SAFETY AND ERGONOMICS (ASER) www.institut-aser.de Germany
	KU LEUVEN www.kuleuven.be/english Belgium
	Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC qplanintl.gr Greece
	ASOCIACIÓN NACIONAL DE EMPRESARIOS FABRICANTES DE ÁRIDOS www.aridos.org Spain
	MULTIMED ENGINEERS SRL www.multimedengineers.com/site Italy
	HIT HYPERTECH INNOVATIONS LTD www.hit-innovations.com Cyprus

ACTIVE HEALTHY PRODUCTIVE AGEING WITH ENHANCED WORKABILITY

PROJECT IDENTITY

H2020 project H2020-SC1-DTH-2018-1
Grant Agreement 826299

RESEARCH AND INNOVATION ACTION
Start 01/01/2019
Duration 36 months
EU Contribution 3.995.750,00 €
Target groups Ageing workers mostly performing manual labor, large private and public industrial companies (HR, OSH)

FIND OUT MORE ABOUT THE PROJECT

VISIT: www.ageingatwork-project.eu
CONTACT US: kvotis@iti.gr

FOLLOW US:
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 AgeingatWork Project
 ageingatwork project

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Ageing@Work
www.ageingatwork-project.eu

Figure 2. Side A Ageing@Work's leaflet

Ageing@Work's ICT TOOLS

All these personalized and adaptive ICT tools will be fused in a novel, integrated platform, complemented by a virtual coach through a mirroring user avatar and a personalized reward-based motivation system to promote positive behaviors both at work and at home (physical activity, dietary habits, etc.). Along these tools, an age-friendly management DSS will be provided to company managers

EXPECTED BENEFITS

- 1. WORK CO-DESIGN TOOLS**
Personalized ergonomics design tool, to improve the physical design of the workplace and age-friendly work management assistant tool, to assist in workers' task assignment and scheduling
- 2. WORKABILITY AND PRODUCTIVITY ENHANCEMENT TOOLS**
 - a) Telepresence tool to allow remote collaboration to the ageing worker from home or on-site,
 - b) Lifelong training tool based on VR and AR, to facilitate the older worker into the learning of new processes,
 - c) Knowledge sharing and collaboration platform to help provide the ageing worker's experience and skills to younger co-workers.
- 3. VIRTUAL COACH**
Virtual coach through a mirroring user avatar and a personalized reward-based motivation system to promote positive behaviors both at work and at home (physical activity, dietary habits, etc.).

SENIOR WORKERS

- Improved productivity and work flexibility
- Increased motivation and work satisfaction
- Age-friendly working and living conditions
- Prevention of health problems

INDUSTRIAL COMPANIES

- Increased productivity
- Retention of experienced workers
- Better informed decision making, Human Resources and Occupational Health and Safety management
- Lower company costs for work-related health problems and work accidents
- Corporate social responsibility

Figure 3. Side B Ageing@Work's leaflet

2.1.3 Poster

To complete the dissemination material promotional package available for the dissemination activities of Ageing@Work project, a Poster has been created (see [Figure 4](#)) following the same overall layout designed for the project. This is a version created for a generic audience, that can be used in stands or booths and contain the project web page.

Figure 4. Ageing@Work's poster

2.1.4 Templates

Templates for the project’s deliverables and for the partners’ presentations have been created for the consortium partners to be able to produce their project deliverables and their presentations following the visual identity of the project. These can be found in the Annexes of this deliverable.

2.2 Dissemination channels

2.2.1 Ageing@Work web portal

The Ageing@Work website serves as the primary online platform to provide information about Ageing@Work, the project objectives, concept and results and provides access to news about the project. The Ageing@Work website also cross links with all the social media channels of the project.

Activities related to the website during the first 18 months consisted in:

- Defining the content and structure of the website
- Booking the domain names and setting up the IT infrastructure
- Designing, developing and publishing the website
- Refining the existing content and adding new content (news, results, etc.)

Since the launch of the website on February 2019 until June 2020, there were 1322 sessions by 1007 users for a total of 2867 page views. An average session duration on the website is 01:46 minutes (counted as the period of time a user is actively engaged with the website).

Figure 5. Ageing@Work web portal traffic. Source: Google Analytics.

Concerning the audience, 11% are returning visitors, while 89% are new visitors. Thus, we can make a positive conclusion that Ageing@Work attracts new visitors who would like to learn more about the project and its development.

Figure 6. Ageing@Work web portal: new visitors vs returning visitors. Source: Google Analytics

The most popular countries among our audience are Greece (234 users), United States (135 users), Spain (95 users), Germany (82 users), United Kingdom (58 users), Italy (38), India (32), Poland (32), the Netherlands (22) and France (21).

Figure 7. Ageing@Work web portal: geographical scope of audience. Source: Google Analytics.

Country ?	Acquisition			Behavior		
	Users ? ↓	New Users ?	Sessions ?	Bounce Rate ?	Pages / Session ?	Avg. Session Duration ?
	1,007 % of Total: 100.00% (1,007)	1,008 % of Total: 100.10% (1,007)	1,322 % of Total: 100.00% (1,322)	48.87% Avg for View: 48.87% (0.00%)	2.17 Avg for View: 2.17 (0.00%)	00:01:46 Avg for View: 00:01:46 (0.00%)
1. Greece	234 (23.05%)	232 (23.02%)	403 (30.48%)	39.45%	2.50	00:02:10
2. United States	135 (13.30%)	135 (13.39%)	136 (10.29%)	96.32%	1.06	00:00:04
3. Spain	95 (9.36%)	94 (9.33%)	128 (9.68%)	37.50%	2.56	00:02:48
4. Germany	82 (8.08%)	82 (8.13%)	99 (7.49%)	39.39%	2.34	00:01:53
5. United Kingdom	58 (5.71%)	57 (5.65%)	76 (5.75%)	35.53%	2.97	00:02:13
6. Italy	38 (3.74%)	37 (3.67%)	49 (3.71%)	30.61%	2.41	00:03:03
7. India	32 (3.15%)	32 (3.17%)	37 (2.80%)	75.68%	1.19	00:00:36
8. Poland	32 (3.15%)	31 (3.08%)	59 (4.46%)	27.12%	2.80	00:02:14
9. Netherlands	22 (2.17%)	22 (2.18%)	22 (1.66%)	54.55%	1.68	00:01:02
10. France	21 (2.07%)	21 (2.08%)	23 (1.74%)	34.78%	2.26	00:01:17

Figure 8. Ageing@Work web portal: geographical metrics of top 10 countries. Source: Google Analytics.

The information on the most visited pages demonstrates that apart from regular landing pages, such as “Objectives” and “Concept and approach”, visitors are mostly interested in the Ageing@Work newsletter.

Page ?	Pageviews ? ↓	Unique Pageviews ?	Avg. Time on Page ?	Entrances ?	Bounce Rate ?
	2,867 % of Total: 100.00% (2,867)	2,201 % of Total: 100.00% (2,201)	00:01:29 Avg for View: 00:01:29 (0.00%)	1,318 % of Total: 100.00% (1,318)	48.87% Avg for View: 48.87% (0.00%)
1. /	1,074 (37.46%)	773 (35.12%)	00:01:55	693 (52.58%)	47.04%
2. /newsletter/ageingatwork-newsletter	218 (7.60%)	120 (5.45%)	00:01:10	72 (5.46%)	32.88%
3. /content/ageingatwork-concept-outputs	185 (6.45%)	153 (6.95%)	00:01:48	47 (3.57%)	59.57%
4. /content/objectives-ageingwork-project	177 (6.17%)	148 (6.72%)	00:02:29	108 (8.19%)	57.41%
5. /partners	120 (4.19%)	92 (4.18%)	00:00:42	9 (0.68%)	88.89%
6. /projects	102 (3.56%)	56 (2.54%)	00:02:20	20 (1.52%)	52.38%
7. /public-deliverables	73 (2.55%)	69 (3.13%)	00:00:20	2 (0.15%)	33.33%
8. /content/publications	69 (2.41%)	57 (2.59%)	00:01:44	9 (0.68%)	33.33%
9. /subscribe/confirm	69 (2.41%)	57 (2.59%)	00:00:49	0 (0.00%)	0.00%
10. /content/dissemination-material	67 (2.34%)	59 (2.68%)	00:01:32	10 (0.76%)	70.00%

Figure 9. Ageing@Work web portal: most visited pages. Source: Google Analytics.

The following image shows where the traffic on the Ageing@Work web portal comes from. We can conclude that direct landing, organic search and referral from social networks are the 3 top routes leading to the website so far.

Top Channels

Figure 10. Ageing@Work web portal: source of website traffic. Source: Google Analytics.

From the above graphics and figures, we can conclude that efforts need to be made in the next period to:

- Increase the traffic to the website.

- Increase the traffic through organic search and through referral.

To achieve this, we will need to work on several fronts:

- Content: There is a need to improve the content available on the website. This will certainly be the case when the Ageing@Work pilots are set in motion and we have actual results from the Ageing@Work platform in the field (parallel development of Ageing@Work promotional video).
- Generating more back links to the website to generate more traffic through referrals.

2.2.2 Newsletter

Online newsletter distribution provides the opportunity to increase public and stakeholders' awareness of the project, assists increasing the outreach to the target audience and maintaining contact with it, and encourages readers to find out more about the project, including links to more detailed information on project's website.

Within Ageing@Work dissemination activities, an online newsletter was regularly distributed among various project stakeholders and the newsletter subscribers, on a semester basis. Three issues of the Ageing@Work newsletter have been released, until the end of M18 (June 2020).

For the distribution of the newsletter, the professional web marketing solution MailChimp was used. After its release, the newsletter was published on the project's official web portal and is further disseminated through the project's social media accounts.

AGEING@WORK NEWSLETTER

JUN
23
2020

3RD ISSUE OF THE AGEING@WORK NEWSLETTER

By contentuser

The 3rd issue of the [Ageing@Work](#) newsletter has just been released ! Read the [Ageing@Work](#) Newsletter N.3 here! Subscribe to our Newsletter to stay tuned!

FEB
17
2020

2ND ISSUE OF THE AGEING@WORK NEWSLETTER

By contentuser

The 2nd issue of the [Ageing@Work](#) newsletter has just been shared with the newsletter subscribers and various project stakeholders. This issue refers to the progress of the 1st year and introduces our first achievements! Read the [Ageing@Work](#) Newsletter and subscribe to our Newsletter to stay tuned!

Check out the 2nd newsletter [here!](#)

JUL
19
2019

1ST ISSUE OF THE AGEING@WORK NEWSLETTER

By contentuser

The 1st issue of the [Ageing@Work](#) newsletter has just been shared with various project stakeholders! This issue introduces the project and refers to the progress of the first 6 months, highlighting the main activities and achievements.

Figure 11. Ageing@Work newsletters uploaded on the Ageing web portal upon release.

The basic distribution list contains 95 stakeholders who have subscribed to the newsletter through the respective section on the Ageing@Work web portal.

Audience performance

Top locations

Figure 12. Newsletter statistics. Source: Mailchimp

News and information about Ageing@Work is also promoted through the semesterly newsletter of the WorkingAge H2020 project (HORIZON 2020 RIA GA: 826232), which holds a distribution list of approximately 45 stakeholders.

2.2.3 Social media accounts

1.1.1.1 Usage of Twitter channel

The project Twitter channel was established in February 2019. The dissemination efforts on the Twitter channel include compiling short messages which can be posted on this channel. To this end, the Dissemination Manager seeks for general messages which could be relevant for our stakeholders and increase our followers base. Several sources are used to compile messages:

- by searching on relevant acknowledged sources of information such as EU-OSHA, PEROSH, Eurofound, CEDEFOP, etc.
- Retweet content twitted by our followers or by potential influencers identified by the Dissemination Manager. When twitting these messages, chances are increased to engage these influencers and widen our outreach.

In the first period of Ageing@Work, the Ageing@Work Twitter channel was mainly used to virally spread out news and messages, especially information about workplace and OSH news and events, partner activities, etc., in order to start building an online presence and widen our network comprised from relevant stakeholders.

Identifying relevant stakeholders and following them or publishing specific messages mentioning them was also a way to raise their interest to follow us. At the time of writing this deliverable (June 2020), the Ageing@Work's twitter account counts 106 followers.

Figure 13. Ageing@Work Twitter statistics. Source Twitter (June 2020).

Figure 14. Followers of Ageing@Work twitter page during the last 18 months. Source: Twitter

Figure 15. Profile visits of Ageing@Work twitter page during the last 18 months. Source: Twitter

Figure 16. Ageing@Work tweet impressions during the last 18 months. Source: Twitter.

The above graphics and figures show that the engagement strategy followed for the twitter channel started to bring satisfactory results. The channel is set to grow but there is a need to step up the related efforts as there is a huge potential to build a big followers base on twitter.

1.1.1.2 Usage of LinkedIn channel

On LinkedIn, the Ageing@Work project is active with a company account. The account was launched on February 2019 and currently it has 249 followers.

Figure 17. Ageing@Work LinkedIn follower statistics from May 2019 to May 2020. Source: LinkedIn.

Figure 18. Visitors of the LinkedIn page of Ageing@Work from May 2019 to May 2020. Source: LinkedIn.

Some of the most successful posts so far are presented below.

Figure 19. Statistics on LinkedIn posts and respective impressions (1/2). Source: LinkedIn.

Update engagement		Time range: Jun 22, 2019 - Jun 22, 2020		Show: 20						
Update title	Posted by	Created	Impressions	Video views	Clicks	CTR	Reactions	Comments	Shares	Foll
New European Guidance on COVID-19: Back to the workplace - Adapting workplaces... All followers	Christina Balla	6/16/2020	82	-	1	1.22%	1	0	0	
Safer and healthier work at any age data visualisation tool All followers	Christina Balla	4/28/2020	125	-	0	0%	5	0	0	
The 4th Project Meeting was organised in Warsaw, Poland at the premises of CIOP-.... All followers	Christina Balla	3/4/2020	277	-	44	15.88%	13	0	4	
2nd day at the 4th project meeting in Warsaw and partners surely look excited!... All followers	Christina Balla	2/21/2020	304	-	41	13.49%	16	0	0	
All consortium partners have gathered in Warsaw for a two-day meeting to assess t... All followers	Christina Balla	2/19/2020	178	-	14	7.87%	11	0	4	
2nd issue of the Ageing@Work newsletter All followers	Christina Balla	1/23/2020	139	-	4	2.88%	11	0	3	
AGEINGATWORK Newsletter Ageing At Work All followers	Christina Balla	1/13/2020	216	-	6	2.78%	9	0	5	
Increasing the value of age All followers	Christina Balla	1/7/2020	99	-	1	1.01%	6	0	0	

Figure 20. Statistics on LinkedIn posts and respective impressions (2/2). Source: LinkedIn.

1.1.1.3 Usage of Facebook channel

The Facebook account was established on February 2019 and is seen as an important channel to publish relevant news, events and information relative to the Ageing@Work project. As of June 2020, the Facebook page of Ageing@Work counted 80 page likes and 87 followers. Since the account was created, a lot of posts were published by the Dissemination Manager. More information on the posts of July 2019 – June 2020 and their outreach is presented in the figure below.

Published	Post	Type	Targeting	Reach	Engagement
06/16/2020 1:45 PM					
04/28/2020 12:35 PM					
03/04/2020 10:39 AM					
02/21/2020 3:53 PM					

Figure 21. Ageing@Work Facebook posts analysis (1/2). Source: Facebook.

Figure 22. Ageing@Work Facebook posts analysis (2/2). Source: Facebook.

2.2.4 Publications

Throughout the project lifetime scientific publications assisted in informing the academic and research community as well as the industry and general public about the project’s objectives, scientific activities, findings and results. Scientific knowledge generated during the project is already being shared in popular and high ranked scientific conferences and journals, as shown in the table below.

Table 1. Ageing@Work publications

Publication type	Title	Authors	Conference	Partner	Date
Paper in proceedings of a conference	Smart, Personalized and Adaptive ICT Solutions for Active, Healthy and Productive Ageing with enhanced Workability	Dimitrios Giakoumis, Konstantinos Votis, Efthymios Altitsiadis, Sofia Segkouli, Ioannis Paliokas, Dimitrios Tzovaras	PERvasive Technologies Related to Assistive Environments (PETRA) Conference 2019	CERTH/ITI, KUL	June 2019

Paper in proceedings of a conference	Fast mesh denoising with data driven normal filtering using deep autoencoders	Stavros Nousias, Gerasimos Arvanitis, Aris S. Lalos, Konstantinos Moustakas	IEEE 17th International Conference on Industrial Informatics (INDIN) Conference 2019	UPAT	July 2019
Paper in proceedings of a conference	Biophysics-based simulation of virtual human model interactions in 3D virtual scenes	Konstantinos Risvas, Michail Pavlou, Evangelia I. Zacharaki, Konstantinos Moustakas	2020 IEEE Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces Abstracts and Workshops (VRW)	UPAT	March 2020
Publication accepted in ICME Conference	Image-based 3D mesh denoising through a block matching 3D convolutional neural network filtering approach	Gerasimos Arvanitis, Aris S. Lalos, Konstantinos Moustakas	IEEE International Conference on Multimedia and Expo ICME 2020	UPAT	July 2020

The public deliverables will be published on the Ageing@Work web portal as well as on Zenodo with open access once they are accepted by the EU.

2.2.5 Workshops organized

During this period two workshops were organized in the pilot premises. In these workshops a set of co-creation activities were performed with the collaboration of technical developers, ergonomic and work health experts from the Ageing@Work consortium and workers of the involved pilots' sites.

2.2.5.1 Workshop in Madrid (ANEFA Pilot) July 2019

The Spanish workshop took place in Madrid in Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, during July 2019. In the workshop 6 quarry workers from several quarries in Madrid region, 2 ANEFA representatives and 3 technical staff from UPM participated. The structure followed for the workshop was the following: firstly, the 6 participants in the workshop were welcomed, all of them were quarry workers; Secondly, the procedures of the workshop were explained to them, the objective of the project was introduced, and consent forms for participation were signed; After this, a focus group took place, analyzing the 7 preliminary use cases of the ANEFA pilot; Next, the semi-structured interviews were conducted individually and finally the participants were thanked for their collaboration and the farewell was carried out.

Figure 23. Participants in the Madrid first Workshop

2.2.5.2 Workshop in Braunschweig (Siemens Pilot) October 2019

This workshop took place in the Braunschweig Siemens Factory (Germany). In this workshop, technical partners and health work specialists from the Ageing@Work project, along with 20 workers from the factory participated. During the first stage of the workshop, Ageing@Work partners could participate in a visit to the installation in order to better understand the working conditions in the factory. After this stage, several workers (a total of 5) were interviewed in the working locations about their labour conditions and type of work, and how the worker deals with the ageing related conditions in the factory. During these interviews, 20 workers in the factory have participated in the workshop. The workshop details were explained to them and the objective of the project has been introduced as well as the informed consent forms were signed. After that a short questionnaire were filled by the participant workers.

Figure 24. Participants in the Siemens first workshop.

2.2.6 External events

During this period, consortium partners have participated in the following external events.

1. International Conference on Industrial Informatics (<https://www.indin2019.org>) INDIN'19. This event, attended by UPAT during 22-25 July 2019 in Helsinki-Espoo, is an IEEE conference about Industrial application of Artificial Intelligence.
2. PErvasive Technologies Related to Assistive Environments (PETRA) conference (<http://www.petrae.org/>). This event, was attended by CERTH during 5-7 June 2019 in Aldemar Amilia Mare, Rhodes, Greece, and was organized by the University of Texas at Arlington, USA. The conference is a highly interdisciplinary conference that focuses on computational and engineering approaches to improve the quality of life and enhance human performance in a wide range of settings, in the workplace, at home, in public spaces, urban environments, and other.
3. Mining and Minerals Hall (AMINER) <https://mmhseville.com> was attended by ANEFA during the 15-17 October 2019 in Sevilla, Spain. Mining and Minerals Hall (AMINER) was a world meeting that gathered the present and future knowledge of mining.
4. Work-related stress and mental health at work workshop (Perosh) <https://perosh.eu/hse-workshop-on-work-related-stress/> was attended by CIOP-PIB during 7-8.05.2019. CIOP has participated therein with an oral presentation of the Ageing@Work project and its core activities.
5. ASER participated in an ISO-Meeting held in Sydney, Australia on November 2019. There, ASER had the opportunity to distribute more than 30 pieces of Ageing@Work's promotional material (i.e. leaflet).

2.3 Synergies

Synergies with other EU-funded or international research projects and initiatives in the relevant research domains are constantly pursued to facilitate knowledge exchange, to gain mutual dissemination benefits and to exploit potential collaborations. Possible synergies include (without being limited to) the following actions:

- inclusion of the project web-portal and social media as links in websites and social media of other projects,
- participation in events of similar projects,
- dissemination of Ageing@Work promotional material in events of similar projects,
- invitations to participate in Ageing@Work events, and
- exchange of news/invitations and dissemination through other projects' channels.

In this direction, during the first half of the project, Ageing@Work has collaborated with several relevant H2020 projects in order to boost its visibility and outreach. In particular Ageing@Work has implemented joined actions with WorkingAge (H2020 GA: 826232), sustAGE (H2020 GA:826506), BIONIC (GA: 826304), SmartWork (H2020 GA: 826343), SeeFAR (H2020 GA: 826429), COADAPT (H2020 GA: 826266) and ACTIVAGE (H2020 GA: 732679). These actions encompass preparation of joint publications and press

releases, invitations to each other’s events, promotion through the projects’ web portals, cross promotion through newsletters, and others.

The Dissemination Manager has also prepared some Collaboration Agreements to better substantiate the scope of the synergies, which were sent to Ageing@Work’s synergizing projects and 3 of them have already been signed (i.e. WorkingAge, sustAGE, seeFAR) as shown in Annex III.

Further synergies established with initiatives, actions and networks across Ageing@Work’s social media channels (including PEROSH, SAPHIRe, Leaves: AAL project, Homes4Life, etc.) have been a key element of the project’s dissemination and communication activities, enhancing the outreach of Ageing@Work to various additional stakeholders.

2.4 EU dissemination channel

During this period, the following EU dissemination channels have been used, in order to share with these organizations information related to the project and establish a first contact to collaborate in the next period of the dissemination plan.

- CORDIS (Community Research and Development Information Service). CORDIS web where Ageing@Work consortium and objective are published along with other project information as can be seen in next Figure.

Figure 25. Ageing@Work information on CORDIS.

- Partnership for European research in occupational safety and health (PEROSH). The PEROSH comprises 14 Occupational Safety and Health (OSH) institutes in 13 European countries aims to contribute to research and best practices exchange for full employment, social inclusion and safe and sustainable work. A promotional email informing stakeholder about the value propositions of Ageing@Work was sent to the PEROSH network - 14 Institutions, through the consortium partner CIOP-PIB.

- EU-OSHA Focal Point network of national focal points is vital to the Healthy Workplaces Campaign. They coordinate the Healthy Workplaces Campaign at the national level. The organization involves about 50 organization in 30 different European countries. A promotional email informing stakeholder about the value propositions of Ageing@Work was sent to the was sent to EU-OSHA Focal Point network, with 50 recipients, through the consortium partner CIOP-PIB.

Following steps in the area, in order to continue these first contacts with regards to possible dissemination supported by the networks will be taken.

3. Performance indicators and monitoring

To measure the success of Ageing@Work’s awareness raising and communication strategy, the following KPIs have been employed and all dissemination activities are monitored with their results being compared to the following KPIs so as to assess whether Ageing@Work is on the right path or if increased dissemination efforts need to take place.

Table 2. KPIs and target values

Indicator (KPI)	Target Value (impact)	Current Status
Number of scientific papers published	18 (in scientific conferences and journals)	4
Number of external events / conferences attended	30 events / conferences (research and industrial)	5
Synergies with major initiatives and networks	10 joint actions	18 synergies
Number of visits to the Ageing@Work web-portal	15,000 unique visitors by the end of the project	1017 unique users
Number of followers in the social media accounts	2,000 followers (Facebook, LinkedIn, YouTube and Twitter)	446 Followers (+906 visitors)
Number of promotional material distributed	2,000 copies distributed in project/external events	30
Number of newsletters	6 newsletters (one per semester)	3
Number of workshops / participants in each one	3 workshops / 30 participants per workshop	2 / 25 participants
Number of participants in the Final Conference	100 participants (academia, industry and government)	-

To meet these target values, project partners are expected to intensify the communication and dissemination actions in the forthcoming months, putting emphasis on the production of scientific

publications, the attendance of external conferences and events as well as the improvement of website visitors and social media followers.

4. Conclusions

This document presents the activities carried out so far (M18) in the field of dissemination and communication of the Ageing@Work project.

It should be noted that since March 2020 (M15) the crisis due to COVID-19 affected the mobility of citizens of the European Union, as well as the holding of events, conferences, congresses, etc. where a significant number of people could be concentrated. This has undoubtedly affected the participation of the project consortium partners in different external events where the activities being carried out in the project could be disseminated.

Furthermore, due to security measures both in Germany, in the Siemens factories, and in Spain, in the ANEFA quarries, it was not possible to carry out planned workshops with the workers and personnel of the pilots. We hope that in the near future the situation will be resolved. In any case, we will take all necessary actions in order to ensure that these workshops will be held again and also the participation in communication and dissemination events throughout Europe will be possible.

In the updated version of this deliverable, namely in “D8.8 Ageing@Work Communication and Dissemination Activities – v2”, which will be prepared at the end of the project, the cumulative impact of the Ageing@Work project will be presented.

Annex I Deliverable Template

Ageing@Work

Smart, Personalized and Adaptive ICT Solutions for Active,
Healthy and Productive Ageing with enhanced Workability

Project Acronym:	Ageing@Work
Project Full Name:	Smart, Personalized and Adaptive ICT Solutions for Active, Healthy and Productive Ageing with enhanced Workability
Grant Agreement:	No 826299
Project Duration:	3 years (starting 1 January 2019)

Deliverable X.x

Xxxx

Work Package:	WPX:xxx
Task:	TX.X
Lead Beneficiary:	Partner
Due Date:	Xx/xx/xxxx
Submission Date:	Xx/xx/xxxx
Deliverable Status:	Draft/Final
Deliverable Style:	R
Dissemination Level:	CO/PU
File Name:	Dx.x xxx.pdf

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 826299

Annex II Presentation Template

Ageing@Work

Smart, Personalized and Adaptive ICT Solutions for Active, Healthy and Productive Ageing with enhanced Workability

WPX....

Partner
Name

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation under grant agreement no 826299.

Questions and Answers

Smart, Personalized and Adaptive ICT Solutions for Active, Healthy and Productive Ageing with enhanced Workability

Contact details:

*Presenter, Affiliation
Email etc.*

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation under grant agreement no 826299.

Annex III Collaboration Agreements with Ageing@Work's synergies

Collaboration Agreement

This Collaboration Agreement (hereinafter referred to as "the Agreement") is signed between:

Party 1: Ageing@Work, "Smart, Personalised and Adaptive ICT Solutions for Active, Healthy and Productive Ageing with enhanced Workability", having received funding from the EU's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (GA 826299) and represented for the purposes of signing the Agreement by Evangelia Tsagaraki, Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL, Ageing@Work Dissemination Manager and WP8 Leader.

Party 2: sustAGE, "Smart environments for person-centered sustainable work and well-being", having received funding from the EU's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (GA 826506) and represented for the purposes of signing the Agreement by Petros Patias, AUTH - Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, sustAGE Dissemination Manager and WP7 Leader.

Hereinafter collectively referred to as "Parties".

The Parties signing the Agreement aim to establish a strong liaison between them, in terms of bilaterally implementing the following agreed actions. The Agreement shall be into force during the agreed period or until termination of the agreement by either Party. **Now, therefore, it is hereby agreed as follows:**

Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL on behalf of Ageing@Work agrees to the following:

- Create a collaborative effort with sustAGE on dissemination and communication activities.
- Announce relevant news of sustAGE through Ageing@Work's website and newsletter.
- Distribute relevant sustAGE announcements on Ageing@Work's Social Media Platforms.
- Invite sustAGE representatives to participate in suitable events organized by Ageing@Work.

AUTH on behalf of sustAGE agrees to the following:

- Create a collaborative effort with Ageing@Work on dissemination and communication activities.
- Announce relevant news of Ageing@Work through sustAGE's website and newsletter.
- Distribute relevant Ageing@Work announcements on sustAGE's Social Media Platforms.
- Invite Ageing@Work representatives to participate in suitable events organized by sustAGE.

Duration:

- Starting from the 1st of March 2020 and ending on the 31st of December 2021.

Termination:

- Either Party may terminate the Agreement immediately by notice upon the other Party.

Title: Professor AUTH,
Dissemination Manager of sustAGE

Title: Dissemination Manager of
Ageing@Work

Collaboration Agreement

This Collaboration Agreement (hereinafter referred to as “the Agreement”) is signed between:

Party 1: Ageing@Work, “Smart, Personalised and Adaptive ICT Solutions for Active, Healthy and Productive Ageing with enhanced Workability”, having received funding from the EU’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (GA 826299) and represented for the purposes of signing the Agreement by Evangelia Tsagaraki, Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL, Ageing@Work Dissemination Manager and WP8 Leader.

Party 2: WorkingAge, “Smart Working environments for all Ages”, having received funding from the EU’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (GA 826232) and represented for the purposes of signing the Agreement by Estefanía Arribas, INTRAS FOUNDATION, WorkingAge Communication & Dissemination Manager and WP10 Leader.

Hereinafter collectively referred to as “Parties”.

The Parties signing the Agreement aim to establish a strong liaison between them, in terms of bilaterally implementing the following agreed actions. The Agreement shall be into force during the agreed period or until termination of the agreement by either Party.

Now, therefore, it is hereby agreed as follows:

Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL on behalf of Ageing@Work agrees to the following:

- Create a collaborative effort with WorkingAge on dissemination and communication activities.
- Announce relevant news of WorkingAge through Ageing@Work’s newsletter.
- Distribute relevant WorkingAge announcements on Ageing@Work’s Social Media Platforms.
- Invite WorkingAge representatives to participate in suitable events organized by Ageing@Work.
- Participate in joint actions with WorkingAge such as webinars, conferences and seminars with similar goals, when considered of mutual interest.

INTRAS FOUNDATION on behalf of WorkingAge agrees to the following:

- Create a collaborative effort with Ageing@Work on dissemination and communication activities.
- Announce relevant news of Ageing@Work through WorkingAge’s newsletter.

- Distribute relevant Ageing@Work announcements on WorkingAge's Social Media Platforms.
- Invite Ageing@Work representatives to participate in suitable events organized by WorkingAge.
- Participate in joint actions with Ageing@Work such as webinars, conferences and seminars with similar goals, when considered of mutual interest.

Duration:

- Starting from the 1st of March 2020 and ending on the 31st of December 2021.

Termination:

- Either Party may terminate the Agreement immediately by notice upon the other Party.

WorkingAge

Title: C&D manager, WP 10 leader

Ageing@Work

Title: Dissemination Manager of
Ageing@Work

Collaboration Agreement

This Collaboration Agreement (hereinafter referred to as "the Agreement") is signed between:

Party 1: Ageing@Work, "Smart, Personalised and Adaptive ICT Solutions for Active, Healthy and Productive Ageing with enhanced Workability", having received funding from the EU's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (GA 826299) and represented for the purposes of signing the Agreement by Evangelia Tsagaraki, Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL, Ageing@Work Dissemination Manager and WP8 Leader.

Party 2: See Far, "Smart glasses for multifaceted visual loss mitigation and chronic disease prevention indicator for healthier, safer, and more productive workplace for ageing population", having received funding from the EU's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (GA 826232) and represented for the purposes of signing the Agreement by Aarón Martín. MUSTHAVE SUNGLASSES, See Far Dissemination/Exploitation manager and WP7 Leader.

Hereinafter collectively referred to as "Parties".

The Parties signing the Agreement aim to establish a strong liaison between them, in terms of bilaterally implementing the following agreed actions. The Agreement shall be into force during the agreed period or until termination of the agreement by either Party. **Now, therefore, it is hereby agreed as follows:**

Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL on behalf of Ageing@Work agrees to the following:

- Create a collaborative effort with See Far on dissemination and communication activities.
- Announce relevant news of See Far through Ageing@Work's website and newsletter.
- Distribute relevant See Far announcements on Ageing@Work's Social Media Platforms.
- Invite See Far representatives to participate in suitable events organized by Ageing@Work.

MUSTHAVE SUNGLASSES on behalf of See Far agrees to the following:

- Create a collaborative effort with Ageing@Work on dissemination and communication activities.
- Announce relevant news of Ageing@Work through See Far's website and newsletter.
- Distribute relevant Ageing@Work announcements on See Far's Social Media Platforms.
- Invite Ageing@Work representatives to participate in suitable events organized by See Far.

Duration:

- Starting from the 1st of March 2020 and ending on the 30th of November 2021.

Termination:

- Either Party may terminate the Agreement immediately by notice upon the other Party.

Ageing@Work

Per:

Name:

Title: